

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF CURRENT ECONOMIC CRISIS ON FEMALE EDUCATION AT HIGHER LEVEL

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Abstract

This study assesses the extent of the economic crisis in Pakistan and its implications for female education at the bachelor's level, exploring its effect on the quality of education for women. Employing a qualitative research design, the study uses purposive sampling to conduct in-depth interviews with female students, providing rich qualitative insights into their experiences during this challenging period. The research examines enrollment trends, financial barriers, and socio-economic factors affecting female students' entry into and persistence within bachelor's programs. Initial findings reveal a troubling decline in female enrollment, primarily due to financial constraints and competing household priorities exacerbated by the economic downturn.

Introduction

Countries cannot achieve comprehensive development without education. Education serves as a dual-force agent, propelling economic growth and acting as a tool against poverty (Guo, Liu, & Xu, 2025). It nurtures human capabilities, driving economic advancement through skills acquisition. Nations with significant human capital attract investor interest due to the promise of a skilled workforce. Investment in education is crucial for individual empowerment and fostering national prosperity. The role of education aligns closely with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 4: Quality Education, which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all. The significance of Gender

Equality in society is explicitly outlined in UN Sustainable Development Goal 5 (UN, 2016): Gender equality is not just a fundamental human right but also an essential cornerstone for creating a peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable world. The link between education and economic empowerment becomes even more pronounced when considering income equality. Education serves economic objectives among various other goals. Babatunde & Adefabi (2005) contend that education plays a pivotal role in stimulating economic growth by influencing factors such as expanding employment opportunities, enhancing health facilities, reducing fertility and poverty rates, fostering technological development, and serving as a source of political stability. In

Pakistan, both private and public education sectors encounter numerous challenges (Derkenbaeva, Galushkina, Soodonbekova, Beksultanov, & Kozubekova 2025). Historically, education has been marginalized in the country, facing issues such as insufficient investment, high levels of inflation and poverty, income disparities, gender and regional inequalities, substandard conditions in public educational institutions, elevated fees in private educational institutions, diverse education systems, societal influences, inadequate educational policies, and ineffective implementation (Asian Development Bank (2023). These factors have posed significant obstacles to educational development and the accumulation of human capital in Pakistan.

Khalatur, Honcharenko, et, al. (2022) says that throughout history, economic downturns have been intrinsically linked to transformative shifts in education patterns, emphasizing the domineering for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to comprehend these dynamics. While both genders are undoubtedly affected by the repercussions of economic crises, this research directs its attention to the distinctive challenges encountered by female students pursuing Bachelor's degrees. The rationale behind this deliberate focus emanates from a keen awareness of the enduring gender disparities in educational access and attainment, disparities that economic crises often magnify. The impact of economic downturns on education is multifaceted, encompassing disruptions in funding, changes in job market demands, and altered institutional priorities (Callan, P. M. (2002). However, female students navigating the terrain of higher education during such crises confront additional hurdles. Persistent gender inequalities in access to educational resources and opportunities may intensify, potentially impeding the academic progress of women pursuing Bachelor's degrees. Economic constraints may disproportionately affect female students, leading to increased financial burdens and, consequently, higher dropout rates.

Problem of this study is that the economic challenges extend beyond immediate financial burdens, profoundly affecting not only the educational trajectory but also the long-term

prospects of female students. Dropping out disrupts the continuity of their education, impacting their ability to acquire skills necessary for competitive employment. The economic crisis has a cascading effect on social support systems. Families facing financial strain may struggle to provide necessary encouragement and assistance, exacerbating feelings of isolation and intensifying the pressure on female students, potentially leading to higher dropout rates. The purpose of this research is to assess the extent of the economic crisis in Pakistan and its implication for female education and to explore the effect of economic crisis on the quality of education for female in Pakistan.

Literature review

Filippetti, & Archibugi, (2011) research emphasizes the gendered dimensions of economic crises, highlighting their non-uniform impact across demographics. Females, already contending with pre-existing barriers to educational access, confront exacerbated challenges during economic downturns (Kabeer, N. (2012). The literature underscores the necessity for nuanced analyses that account for the inter sectionalism of gender, class, and race in comprehending the diverse consequences on female education. Economic crises intensify existing inequalities, magnifying disparities in educational opportunities and outcomes for women (Blanton, R., Blanton, S., & Peksen, D. (2019). Recognizing the multifaceted nature of these challenges is imperative for formulating effective policies that address the unique vulnerabilities faced by female students, particularly at the intersection of socio-economic factors. Such insights contribute to the development of strategies fostering educational resilience and equity, acknowledging the intricate interplay of gender dynamics within the broader context of economic fluctuations.

The gendered implications of economic downturns are significant, with women often experiencing disproportionate hardships compared to men. Research by Kahn, J. R., & Bearak, J. M. (2010) titled Gendered Economic Conditions and Suicides underscores this, revealing that economic recessions tend to have a

more pronounced impact on women's mental health and well-being, leading to increased rates of suicide and psychological distress among women (Marazziti, D., Avella, M. T., Mucci, N., Della Vecchia, A., Ivaldi, T., Palermo, S., & Mucci, F. (2021). This highlights the urgent need for gender-sensitive policy responses to mitigate the adverse effects of economic crises on women and promote gender equality in times of hardship (Talamonti, D., Schneider, J., Gibson, B., & Forshaw, M. (2024).

According to Seguino, S. (2010), the effects of the 2008 global financial crisis were profound, marked by widespread job losses and economic upheaval. This turmoil was compounded by the escalation of inequality within and between nations. The widening wealth gap suppressed overall demand and placed low-income households in a perilous cycle of borrowing to maintain basic living standards. This crisis underscores a pivotal moment for the reassessment of macroeconomic policies. Feminist economists are at the forefront, advocating for a recalibration that prioritizes job creation, economic stability, and equity across diverse socio-economic strata encompassing class, gender, and ethnicity (Yolusever, A. (2024). Such an approach recognizes that sustainable recovery hinges on addressing the root causes of inequality and ensuring that the benefits of economic growth are shared equitably.

During economic crises, educational funding often undergoes changes, leading to heightened tuition costs (Mitchell, M., Leachman, M., & Saenz, M. (2019). This financial upheaval poses challenges, particularly affecting marginalized groups, exacerbating disparities in educational access and affordability. Research, exemplified by Blumenstyk, G. (2015), underscores the disproportionate impact of financial barriers on female students during economic crises, potentially resulting in diminished enrollment and elevated dropout rates (Strielkowski, W., Volchik, V., Maskaev, A., & Savko, P. (2020). This gendered disparity emphasizes the urgency of implementing targeted financial aid programs specifically tailored to address the unique challenges faced by women pursuing Bachelor's

degrees. Recognizing and addressing these financial hurdles is crucial to fostering inclusivity and mitigating the adverse effects of economic downturns on female education, promoting resilience and equitable access to higher education opportunities. Antonopoulos, (2009) reveals that two critical global concerns dominate discussions worldwide. Firstly, there's the urgent need to contain the vast financial sector crisis. Efforts to inject massive liquidity and implement various measures aimed at preventing a global financial meltdown are underway.

The literature emphasizes the crucial role of institutional and policy-level responses in alleviating the repercussions of economic crises on female education. Arentsen, Bressers, & Toole (2000) propose initiatives such as targeted scholarship programs, flexible academic policies, and career counseling services as effective measures. These strategies aim to provide comprehensive support for female students, addressing financial constraints and facilitating educational resilience amid challenging economic climates (Putri, G. A. (2024). By implementing such interventions, institutions can proactively contribute to mitigating the impact of economic uncertainties, fostering an environment that empowers and sustains the educational pursuits of women at the higher education level. While the full ramifications of the ongoing financial and economic crisis on women remain uncertain, historical precedents and preliminary insights from contemporary research suggest a concerning possibility: the potential reversal of strides made in gender equality and women's empowerment. Past crises have consistently demonstrated that women often bear a disproportionate brunt of economic downturns, grappling with job losses, diminished access to economic opportunities, and heightened caregiving responsibilities (World Health Organization. (2024). Early indications from current studies echo these patterns, hinting at similar vulnerabilities emerging amidst the current crisis. Women, predominantly concentrated in sectors acutely affected by economic turbulence, face heightened risks of unemployment and financial insecurity. Moreover, the closure of educational institutions and childcare facilities

exacerbates caregiving duties for many women, impeding their full participation in the workforce. These factors collectively pose a formidable threat to the hard-won progress in gender equality and women’s empowerment.

Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research design to delve into the intricate experiences of female students pursuing Bachelor's degrees amidst ongoing economic crises. Through qualitative methods including in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and document analysis, the study aims to uncover the nuanced dimensions of how economic downturns impact female education. In-depth interviews offer a platform for individual female students to articulate their personal experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms during economic instability. Population includes females pursuing undergraduate degrees in disciplines such as biology, chemistry, physics, mathematics, engineering, computer science, and other related fields. By examining the challenges and barriers

faced by female students amidst the economic crisis. The study utilizes purposive sampling to investigate the impact of the current economic crisis on female education at the Bachelor's level. Thematic analysis, employed to investigate the impact of the current economic crisis on female education at the BS level through interviews, involves a systematic process of identifying, analyzing, and interpreting patterns or themes within the collected qualitative data.

Finding and results

The qualitative data obtained from semi-structured interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis. The responses were coded and organized in NVivo-style hierarchical nodes, where initial codes were grouped into categories and broader themes. This coding process enabled the identification of recurring patterns related to financial challenges, access to educational resources, academic performance, and coping strategies among university students during the economic crisis.

Thematic Analysis Table

Interview Item	Codes	Categories	Themes
Item1: Educational Background	8th semester student, BS program, different department of Women’s University	Undergraduate academic status	Final-year undergraduate students in social science disciplines
Item 2: Impact of Economic Crisis on Education	Transportation cost, rent expenses, delayed fee payment, lack of textbooks, reduced job opportunities, increased work hours	Financial burden, employment pressure, limited resources	Economic crisis creates financial barriers affecting educational continuity
Item 3: Access and Affordability of Education	Budget struggle, inability to afford textbooks, difficulty paying fees, financial stress	Financial stress, educational affordability challenges	Economic instability limits students’ ability to afford education
Item 4: Changes in Income or Employment	Decreased income, financial instability, prioritizing spending, seeking financial support	Household income reduction, coping mechanisms	Reduced household income increases financial pressure on education

Item 5: Access to Educational Resources	Lack of textbooks, limited internet access, difficulty obtaining study materials, sharing resources, online libraries	Limited educational resources, alternative resource access	Economic crisis restricts access to educational materials
Item 6: Availability of Educational Resources	Lack of subject books, difficulty obtaining materials, reliance on libraries, sharing resources	Resource scarcity, alternative learning strategies	Limited availability of academic resources during economic hardship
Item 7: Academic Performance	Transportation cost, limited study materials, financial stress	Attendance issues, mental stress, academic performance decline	Financial difficulties negatively affect academic performance
Item 8: Career Aspirations	Reconsidering career goals, choosing stable fields, economic uncertainty	Career reconsideration, economic influence on career choice	Economic crisis influences career decisions and aspirations
Item 9: Coping Strategies	Budget management, reduced spending, family members working, support from relatives	Household financial adjustments, family support	Families adopt financial coping strategies to sustain education
Item 10: Personal Resilience	Unable to buy laptop, lack of phone, expensive materials, late fee penalties	Technology access challenges, financial hardship	Students demonstrate resilience despite financial barriers

Finding

1. The findings from the responses indicate a diverse student body at Women's University with students pursuing various fields of study across different semesters.

2. The findings from the responses highlight various ways in which students' education is affected by economic challenges. Common themes include financial strain, difficulty affording essentials such as textbooks and accommodation, transportation issues, delays in paying fees, and reduced opportunities for part-time work. These factors collectively contribute to increased stress, uncertainty, and compromised focus on academic pursuits. The responses underscore the interconnectedness between economic circumstances and educational outcomes, emphasizing the importance of addressing financial barriers to ensure equitable access to education. Additionally, they shed light

on the multifaceted impacts of economic crises on students' overall well-being, including mental health and academic performance. This suggests a need for comprehensive support systems and interventions to mitigate the adverse effects of economic challenges on students' educational experiences

3. The findings indicate that individuals faced significant financial difficulties and stress during an economic downturn or crisis, particularly regarding their ability to afford essential academic materials and cover educational expenses such as tuition fees and textbooks. This situation forced individuals to make tough decisions about allocating limited funds, often resulting in sacrificing educational needs. The responses also highlight the importance of financial resilience in accessing education, suggesting that economic hardships can profoundly impact individuals' ability to invest in their education. Overall, these

findings underscore the intersection between economic challenges and educational pursuits, emphasizing the need for support mechanisms to help individuals navigate financial strains while pursuing their studies.

4. The findings highlight the significant impact of the economic crisis on individuals' ability to afford educational expenses, particularly semester fees. The statements convey a common theme of decreased income and financial strain, resulting in challenges related to covering essential costs associated with education. Participants express difficulties in managing their finances amidst income fluctuations caused by the economic downturn. They describe prioritizing spending, seeking alternative sources of financial support, and experiencing heightened anxiety about managing educational expenses. Despite these challenges, there is a prevailing determination among participants to overcome financial obstacles and continue their education, even if it requires seeking additional assistance.

5. The findings from the provided responses highlight the significant challenges individuals face in accessing essential educational resources amidst the economic crisis. Participants express difficulties in obtaining textbooks, internet access, and study materials, which are vital for their academic progress. The economic downturn exacerbates existing disparities in resource access, particularly affecting students from disadvantaged backgrounds.

6. The findings from the provided responses underscore the significant impact of economic crises on students' ability to access subject-related resources essential for academic success. Participants express challenges in obtaining textbooks and study materials, which directly affect their engagement and progress in their studies. The economic downturn exacerbates existing difficulties and creates additional barriers to accessing these resources.

7. The findings from these responses suggest that the individual faces significant challenges related to accessing educational resources and transportation due to financial constraints caused by an economic crisis. These challenges have a direct and negative impact on their academic

performance and progress. They often find themselves struggling to afford transportation fare and essential educational materials, leading to difficulties in maintaining regular attendance and excelling academically. The responses highlight the constant juggling act required to allocate funds between transportation expenses and purchasing study materials, which further impedes their academic journey.

8. The findings from these responses indicate that the economic crisis has had a profound impact on individuals' career aspirations and decisions regarding their field of study. The economic challenges, coupled with logistical hurdles such as distance from the university, have prompted individuals to reassess their career goals and consider alternative paths that may be more feasible in the current economic climate. This reevaluation includes weighing job opportunities, stability, and resilience in times of economic instability associated with different fields of study.

9. The findings from these responses suggest that the individuals are facing financial challenges, likely due to the economic crisis. However, they have taken various measures to cope with these challenges and manage their expenses within their monthly income. These measures include family members taking up additional employment, receiving assistance from relatives, and adjusting their daily consumption habits. The goal is to lighten the financial burden and ensure that expenditures align with the available monthly income.

10. The responses provided reflect personal experiences of individuals facing economic challenges, particularly related to managing expenses for education and essential tools like laptops and phones. These experiences demonstrate resilience in the face of adversity, as individuals strive to overcome financial obstacles to pursue their academic and professional goals.

Discussion

Economic challenges profoundly impact the educational journeys and well-being of students at Women's University Mardan. Students face a myriad of financial difficulties, including strained finances, struggles to afford necessities like

textbooks and housing, and transportation issues. These challenges contribute to heightened stress, uncertainty, and decreased academic concentration, ultimately affecting students' mental well-being and academic performance. The close relationship between economic situations and educational achievements is evident, with individuals often forced to make difficult choices regarding the allocation of limited funds, sometimes sacrificing educational necessities. Despite these obstacles, students demonstrate remarkable resilience and determination, adopting various strategies such as seeking extra employment opportunities and adjusting spending habits to persevere in their education. Economic crises exacerbate existing disparities in access to educational resources, particularly impacting students from disadvantaged backgrounds. This hampers students' involvement and advancement in academic pursuits. Economic turmoil also prompts individuals to reevaluate their career goals, leading to a shift towards paths that align better with prevailing economic conditions. To address these challenges, robust financial aid programs, accessible resources, and employment opportunities are essential. Creating an inclusive and supportive environment for all students is crucial for ensuring fair access to education. Insights from this study have significant implications for future research and policy initiatives. Understanding the impact of economic challenges on education can inform the development of effective strategies and interventions to support students facing financial difficulties. By addressing these challenges comprehensively, educational institutions can foster an environment where all students can thrive academically, regardless of their economic circumstances.

Conclusions

The data provides a clear illustration of how economic challenges deeply affect both the educational journeys and general well-being of students at Women's University Mardan. It reveals a wide-ranging student population involved in different fields of study throughout various semesters, indicating that these issues are

widespread and affects students from all backgrounds. Financial difficulties present in various forms, such as strained finances, challenges in affording necessities like textbooks and housing, and issues with transportation. These difficulties together lead to increased stress, a sense of uncertainty, and a decrease in academic concentration, ultimately impacting students' mental well-being and academic performance. The close relationship between economic situations and educational achievements highlights the immediate need to address financial obstacles, ensuring fair access to education for all. During economic downturns, individuals encountered notable financial challenges, leading to difficult choices regarding how to allocate their limited funds, sometimes sacrificing educational necessities. Nonetheless, despite these obstacles, there is a prevailing sense of determination among participants to persevere and pursue their education, even if it requires seeking additional support. The task of accessing essential educational resources becomes increasingly difficult during economic crises, amplifying pre-existing disparities in resource accessibility, especially for students from disadvantaged backgrounds. These barriers directly impact students' involvement and advancement in their academic pursuits. During times of economic turmoil, people find themselves reevaluating their career goals and exploring alternative avenues that align better with the prevailing economic conditions. Despite facing financial difficulties, individuals exhibit resilience by adopting various strategies, such as seeking extra employment opportunities and modifying their spending habits.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that universities and government authorities provide financial assistance such as scholarships and fee concessions to support students affected by the economic crisis. Educational institutions should ensure the availability of affordable or free academic resources including digital textbooks and online learning materials. Universities should also offer

transportation subsidies and affordable hostel facilities to reduce the financial burden on students who live far from campus. Flexible tuition fee policies such as installment plans and delayed payment options should be implemented to help students manage their financial constraints. Institutions should strengthen career counseling services and provide part-time employment opportunities to support students financially during their studies. The government should increase investment in higher education and introduce policies that support economically disadvantaged students. Universities should also introduce technology support programs such as laptop loan schemes and improved internet access to facilitate learning. Additionally, educational institutions should establish student counseling and support services to help students cope with financial stress and maintain their academic performance during economic challenges.

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